

Success Story

Management of splay leg in emu chicks

Rajesh Kumar*, Archana Kumari* and Saroj Kumar**

*Assistant Professor, Deptt. of Vet. Surgery & Radiology, Bihar Veterinary College Patna

** Assistant Professor, Deptt. of Vet. Extension, Bihar Veterinary College Patna

Introduction

Emu is adaptable to a wide range of environmental conditions. Leg deformities are one of the major causes of mortality in emu chicks. Spraddle leg or splay leg is leg deformities that begin when birds are quite immature. It occurs when abnormal lateral forces on leg & feet cause the long bones & sockets of upper leg to distort & bend outward or sideways. Both legs are usually affected. Main cause of this condition is slicky nesting area, abnormal bedding, mycotoxins, deficiencies of Ca and Vit. A, D₃ and high phosphorus.

Total 20 emu chicks with splay leg were recorded in emu farm. Among these 20 emu chicks, fourteen had bilateral leg deformities and six had unilateral leg deformities. Both legs of all emu chicks were tied with an adhesive tape at proximal to ankle i.e., tibiotarsus, so that leg can no longer splay outwards. To protect baby legs a wrap is made on leg by bandage and adhesive tape with the help of ice-cream stick on both medial and lateral side. Bandage applied was not much tight to maintain circulation of the foot. All chicks were also supplemented with Vit. AD3 and Ca 2 ML/Lt. water for one month. All emu chicks provided soft bed that prevent slipping and maintain normal balance over leg. Out of 20 emu chicks, twelve emu chicks were nearly walking normally without leg deformities after 15 to 28 days. Five emu chicks died during period of management and three recover with slight leg splay even after 60 days. Training programme organized by extension department of Bihar Veterinary College Patna. Farmer trained regarding emu farming and management of chick to prevent mortality in chicks. Farmer adapts leg tie and supplementation of mineral and vitamin to prevent leg deformities in emu chicks and thus prevent chick mortality in their farm.

